

THE INFLUENCE OF "WAR AND PEACE" BY L.N. TOLSTOY ON ENGLISH-SPEAKING LITERATURE

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Annotation

The article is devoted to the study of the philosophical views of the philosopher-writer L.N. Tolstoy, relating to issues of war as an antisocial phenomenon in any society. The evolution of Tolstoy's philosophical observations and conclusions throughout his entire writing career is shown, which was formed under the influence of wars and hostilities, in which, among other things, the writer himself took part. In the context of this article, we can give Tolstoy's definition of the concept of "war" and its manifestation in many of the author's works on military topics

Key words: national traits, literature about war, problems of the historical development of mankind, military writer, the latest American literature, historical and philosophical excursions, reproduction of complex syntax

"War and Peace" in the English-speaking literary world

The literary fate of L.N. developed in a peculiar way. Tolstoy in England and the United States of America. The writer had great sympathy for the peoples of these countries and their culture. Many works of English and American writers were among his most pressing literary interests. The role of Stern in shaping the writing skills of the young Leo Tolstoy is well known. It is also known that the attention and respect with which the Russian writer treated the great English realists of the 19th century - W. Thackeray and Charles Dickens, whom he called "the world's genius," "the kind of genius that will be born once every hundred years." In contemporary US literature, L.N. Tolstoy highly regarded the "highly original and courageous" Walt Whitman.

In the USA and England at the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, there were no such direct and crude manifestations of persecution of a Russian writer as there were in France. In these countries, the struggle around him took on more subtle veiled forms compared to France. It was there that many attempts were made to distort the ideological and creative image of L.N. Tolstoy. The abundance of various religious and semi-religious communities, groups and sects in these countries created favorable conditions for the

activities of American and English Tolstoyans. Religious reformers of various persuasions in England and especially in the USA intensively established ties with Russian Tolstoyans and spread in their homeland one-sided, essentially false ideas about the Russian artist of words, trying to portray him as a prophet of a new faith and teacher of life. To such a misinterpretation of the work of L.N. Tolstoy. Many non-religious writers also had a hand in Tolstoy. But at the same time, the works of Lev Nikolayevich, back in the 80s of the 19th century, penetrated the reading circles of England and the USA and found a lively response in the consciousness of the best progressive part of society. The Russian writer helped his English and American readers see the incurable ulcers of the modern system.

In the personal library of L.N. Tolstoy in Yasnaya Polyana preserved books that have long become rare - the first edition of War and Peace in English in six volumes, published in New York in 1886. The subtitle states: "Translated into French by a Russian lady, and from French by Clara Bell." To the numerous mistakes and inaccuracies made by "one Russian lady," Princess I.I. Paskevich, there were also other inaccuracies made by the American translator. Following this first English translation, a second, a third, and a fourth came out - all of them, unfortunately, were unsuccessful. Public interest in L.N. Tolstoy in English-speaking countries - as well as throughout the world - was so great that translations, carried out on an anecdotal level, were widely read, found their way into public and private libraries, and, through the efforts of commercial publishers, were reprinted in both England and the USA. both during the life of the great writer and after his death.

The first serious, conscientious translator of the works of L.N. Tolstoy was introduced into English by Constance Garnet (1862-1946), a truly remarkable woman - an educated philologist, a persistent and skillful promoter of Russian literature in England. She translated into English a total of about seventy volumes of works by Russian writers - not only L.N. Tolstoy, but also N.V. Gogol, I.S. Turgeneva, F.M. Dostoevsky, A.P. Chekhov, "The Past and Thoughts" by A.I. Herzen. It rarely happens that the work of a translator of fiction has received such unanimous approval from the outstanding writers of his time, as was the case with Constance Garnet. Her work was highly appreciated, in particular, by John Galsworthy, who was on friendly terms with the Garnet spouses, as well as Joseph Conrad, Katherine Mansfield; Major US writers also spoke approvingly of her translations. Moreover, sometimes in their minds the name K. Garnet was associated specifically with "War and Peace."

The first translators of “War and Peace” either repeated those omissions and cuts that abounded in the French translation of I.I. Paskevich, or themselves, due to inattention or ignorance of certain Russian words, omitted certain phrases, clumsily copied Russian expressions, introduced Russian words (with or without explanation) into the English text. The translation by K. Garnet was carried out incomparably more carefully. This was a truly complete text, without omissions - it included all the author’s thoughts and the second part of the epilogue. But what is even more important is that it was the work of an English writer with confident command of his language. K. Garnet even before she started working on.

English literature has a long, strong realistic tradition. It was in England, back in the 18th century, that the first artistically mature examples of the realistic novel appeared. The reading public is widely familiar with the works of the “brilliant school” of novelists of the 19th century - Charles Dickens and W. Thackeray, S. Bronte and E. Gaskell. By the time the works of L.N. Tolstoy penetrated into England, the British reader had at his disposal a wealth of narrative literature created by domestic masters of words. However, the works of Lev Nikolayevich, even at their first appearance in English translation, prompted some prominent critics to think that English writers have something to learn from the masters of Russian realism. Under the welcome address received by L.N. Tolstoy from England on his eightieth birthday, along with hundreds of signatures from readers of different ages and professions, were the names of famous literary figures: Thomas Hardy, B. Shaw, George Meredith, Herbert Wells [18; 514]. The eldest of the English writers who came into creative contact with L.N. Thomas Hardy was fat.

In criticism, attempts were made to bring one of his later works closer to the legacy of Leo Tolstoy - the epic-dramatic poem “Dynasts” [18; 515]. The theme of this poem speaks in favor of such a rapprochement (it talks about the Napoleonic wars and the final fall of Napoleon’s power), and its ideological orientation - pronounced historical fatalism.

However, upon closer examination, the similarities between “Dynasts” and “War and Peace” turn out to be primarily external. In the dramatic poem by T. Hardy lacks the folk element that animates the epic of L.N. Tolstoy, there is also a lack of genuine realistic concreteness in the depiction of characters. The philosophy of historical fatalism, which in the Russian writer is expressed in the author’s reasoning, but is refuted by the logic of images, in T. Hardy penetrates deeply into the artistic structure of the poem, into its plot fabric. Historical

figures - kings, ministers, generals - are interpreted by the playwright as puppets, completely dependent on the unknowable "immanent Will". Napoleon is presented by T. Hardy without exaltation, but also without anger, in the end even with a tinge of some pity. The action widely includes a mystical and symbolic element in the form of spirits commenting on historical events.

The dramatic poem "Dynasts," created by Thomas Hardy at the beginning of the twentieth century, reflected the pessimistic mood of the writer, his confusion in the face of the threat of imperialist wars. Here he is very far from the mighty realism of L.N. Tolstoy.

And another prominent English prose writer of the twentieth century, John Galsworthy, throughout his life showed a keen interest in Leo Nikolaevich Tolstoy. He wrote an essay about him in the series "Profiles of Six Novelists," as well as an article "Tolstoy the Novelist," published on the centenary of the writer's birth and subsequently reprinted as a preface to the English edition of "Anna Karenina."

J. Galsworthy's calling card was "The Forsyte Saga," which included ten separate works (six novels and four interlude stories) and which at the same time represents a holistic narrative, welded together by the unity of theme, plot, characters - a narrative that "never becomes sluggish" and keeps the reader in continuous, unrelenting tension. The "territory" of social and national life covered by "Saga" is, of course, smaller than in "War and Peace." Because of this, "The Forsyte Saga," despite its large volume, despite the abundance of characters, and the long-term (much longer than L.N. Tolstoy's "War and Peace") duration of action, is still not an epic in the true sense of the word. sense of the word: the interest of private life too clearly prevails in it over social and national issues. However, the socio-historical theme, of course, is also present in "Saga" - and not only is it present, but also largely determines its artistic originality. Through the history of one family, the author illuminates and interprets the most important historical processes taking place in England.

Tolstoy the expositor found a lively response from the most daring of his English literary contemporaries - Bernard Shaw. One of the significant aspects of B. Shaw's literary activity is his frequent, bold speeches against wars of aggression. The playwright himself says about himself: "Being a humane person, I abhorred murder and violence wherever I encountered it" [28; 1]. Anti-war tendencies are clearly expressed in his plays of the 90s of the 19th century - "Man and War" and "Man of Destiny". In the second of these plays, which takes

place in 1796, the central figure is the young director general Napoleon Bonaparte.

The image of the Corsican conqueror here serves a double function for the writer. B. Shaw sometimes had the habit of entrusting his own thoughts to negative characters, without regard for either the logic of character or stage verisimilitude. Pronouncing a smart and caustic monologue about the British, directed against the aggressive policy of the British Empire, Napoleon acts as a mouthpiece for the ideas of the author himself. And at the same time, he is interpreted in the play as a clearly satirical figure.

Napoleon, as portrayed by B. Shaw, is not a genius or a mysterious chosen one of fate, but a gifted, unscrupulous and cunning adventurer who puts his own career above all else and is ready to sacrifice many human lives for his ambitious goals. "Blood costs nothing, but wine costs money" [28; 8]. This cynical phrase of Napoleon, like a drop of water, reflects both his own selfish nature and the entire wolfish morality of modern society.

B. Shaw's sharply hostile attitude towards the policy of military conquest, towards murder and violence prompts him to persistently debunk stereotyped ideas about military valor. Drawing the appearance of Napoleon, he partly uses Tolstoy's - and very close to his own inclinations - techniques of "removing the halo." Already in the author's introductory remark, Napoleon is portrayed with the help of degrading everyday details in the most prosaic, non-heroic aspect.

It is possible to find certain motifs in other plays by Bernard Shaw that are directly or indirectly related to the works of L.N. Tolstoy. But much more important than all such private points of contact is the kinship of both writers in the essential and most important. Following L.N. Tolstoy and at the same time B. Shaw castigated the aggressive policy of his contemporary society. In his best plays - such as "Mistress Warren's Profession", "The Widower's House", "Candida", and especially in the brilliant play "Major Barbara" - Tolstoy's principle of tearing off all and all masks was refracted in his own way.

William Thackeray belongs to the brilliant galaxy of English realists. He is one of England's greatest satirists. The originality and strength of his talent were manifested in his satirical denunciation of bourgeois-aristocratic society. His contribution to the development of the novel is associated with the development of the form of the novel - a family chronicle that reveals the private life of the characters in an organic connection with social life. W. Thackeray's satire is folk at its core.

The pinnacle of his realistic work is the novel *Vanity Fair*. In the work created during the rise of the Chartist movement, W. Thackeray's social criticism, his realistic generalizations and satirical skill reach their greatest strength. The writer grasped the connection between people of his contemporary society, based on "heartless purity", on the logical power of money. This society appears in his novel as a huge fair where everything is sold and everything is bought. The author is predominantly a satirist and social exposé. For him, the main thing is to reveal the harsh truth of life without any embellishment or illusions.

The title of the novel is "Vanity Fair. A Novel Without a Hero" - borrowed from "The Pilgrim's Progress" by John Bunyan, who created an allegorical image of the marketplace of everyday vanity. W. Thackeray called the bourgeois-aristocratic society of his time "vanity fair," comparing contemporary England to a huge fair.

The genre of W. Thackeray's novel can be defined as a chronicle novel. The life of the heroes is shown in it over several decades - from youth to old age. Compositionally, W. Thackeray's novels are an important achievement of English realism. The ability to convey life in its development, to reveal the process of character formation and to show its conditioning by the social environment - all this testifies to the great power of the writer's talent.

The novel includes events that have gone down in history. The fates of the characters in the novel are connected with the Battle of Waterloo (1815), as a result of which, under the pressure of the Anglo-Dutch and Prussian troops, the army of Napoleon I was defeated, and he himself was forced to abdicate the throne for the second time.

Everyday scenes in the novel alternate with military episodes, the themes of war and peace intersect. The battle scenes and the episodes preceding them were written by W. Thackeray in a satirical and ironic manner. These are the pictures of pleasure balls and endless entertainment that noble gentlemen and ladies who find themselves in Brussels indulge in on the eve of a decisive battle, as well as caustic and mocking remarks about military leaders. And at the same time, the writer is decisive in his condemnation of the inhumanity and irrationality of war: "Meanwhile, Napoleon, hiding behind the shield of border fortresses, prepared an attack that was supposed to plunge these peaceful people into the abyss of rage and blood and for many of them end in death."

And despite the quality of the translation, I would like to note that it was the translations that made the immortal creation of L.N. accessible to a wide circle of readers around the world. Tolstoy.

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